

Orthodontic and Implant Rehabilitation of a Patient with Missing Mandibular Incisors: A Case Report

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Abstract

Introduction: The loss of mandibular incisors, whether congenital or acquired, presents aesthetic, functional, and biomechanical challenges for orthodontists. Restoring anterior guidance, space balance, and smile esthetics and harmony often requires interdisciplinary planning with prosthetic rehabilitation.

Case Report: A 17-year-old female patient reported with a Class I molar and canine relationship. Clinical examination revealed microdontia of tooth 41 along with congenital absence of teeth 31 and 42. Overjet and overbite could not be assessed due to the absence of mandibular anterior teeth. Orthodontic treatment with a 0.022-in MBT fixed appliance system was initiated to redistribute space and align arches while maintaining molar and canine relationships. Sequential archwire progression (0.014-in NiTi to 0.019 × 0.025-in stainless steel) achieved proper space distribution. Therapeutic extraction of 41 was done and CBCT confirmed adequate alveolar bone. Two implants were placed in the 31 and 42 regions. Following osseointegration, screw-retained crowns were delivered. Retention was provided with a fixed mandibular canine-to-canine retainer and a removable maxillary retainer.

Results: Treatment achieved well-aligned arches with preservation of Class I relationships and ideal space for prosthetic rehabilitation. Implant supported crowns successfully restored aesthetics, phonetics, and function. At the 12-month follow-up, occlusion remained stable, with improved esthetics, function, and patient satisfaction.

Discussion: This case underscores the importance of orthodontic biomechanics in space creation and root positioning prior to implant placement. Literature supports that interdisciplinary collaboration is essential for long-term stability and aesthetic success in cases of anterior tooth loss. Implant supported crowns offer a durable and aesthetic alternative compared with space closure or conventional prostheses.

Conclusion: An interdisciplinary orthodontic–prosthodontic approach is essential in managing patients with missing mandibular incisors. Sequential archwire therapy optimized space distribution and root parallelism, enabling successful implant placement and long-term aesthetic and functional outcomes.

Keywords : Class I malocclusion, mandibular incisor agenesis, implant supported restoration, interdisciplinary orthodontics

Introduction

Loss or agenesis of mandibular incisors is uncommon compared with other missing teeth, yet it significantly affects aesthetics, phonetics, and function. Management requires careful consideration of space distribution, occlusal stability, and long-term restorative planning. Orthodontic treatment can optimize space and alignment, while implant supported restorations offer functional and esthetic replacement once growth is complete. This report presents the Interdisciplinary management of a patient with

missing mandibular incisors using fixed orthodontic therapy followed by implant rehabilitation.

Case Report Diagnosis and Etiology

A 17-year-old female presented with the chief complaint of spacing and aesthetic concerns in the lower anterior region. Clinical

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and radiographic examination revealed :

Pretreatment Intraoral and Extraoral

1. Microdontia of tooth 41 along with
2. Congenital absence of teeth 31 and 42
3. Bilateral Class I molar and canine relationship
4. Maxillary arch well aligned; mandibular arch with anterior spacing
5. Overjet and overbite could not be assessed due to the absence of mandibular incisors
6. Favorable periodontal health and adequate alveolar bone in the edentulous region
7. The diagnosis was Angle's Class I malocclusion with missing mandibular central and lateral incisors.

Treatment Objectives

1. Maintain Class I molar and canine relation.
2. Align and level both arches with ideal space distribution.
3. Provide adequate space for replacement of 31, 41, and 42.
4. Restore aesthetics and function through implant-supported prostheses.

Treatment Alternatives

Three Alternatives were Considered

1. Space closure orthodontically with canine substitution rejected due to aesthetic compromise and functional discrepancy.
2. Resin bonded fixed prosthesis not favoured due to reduced long-term predictability.
3. Implant supported restoration after orthodontic space management selected as the most conservative and stable approach.

Treatment Progress

Treatment Progress

Fixed appliance therapy was initiated using a 0.022 in slot MBT prescription preadjusted edgewise appliance system in both arches. The Maxillary arch was bonded for stabilization, while the mandibular arch was bonded to redistribute space in the anterior region and to maintain arch form

1. **Extraction:** Extraction of microdontia teeth 41
2. **Alignment and levelling:** Initial alignment was achieved with 0.014-in NiTi archwires, progressing sequentially through 0.016-in NiTi and 0.018-in NiTi to correct minor rotations and establish proper levelling.
3. **Working Phase:** Progression to rectangular wires (0.017 × 0.025-in NiTi followed by 0.019 × 0.025-in stainless steel) allowed torque expression and arch coordination. During this stage, particular emphasis was placed on space distribution in the mandibular anterior region. Light inter-arch elastics were used selectively to maintain intermaxillary coordination without altering the established Class I molar and canine relation.
4. **Space Management:** Careful monitoring ensured that the space created corresponded to the mesiodistal width of three mandibular incisors. Bolton's analysis and diagnostic wax-up guided space distribution.
5. **Finishing:** Finishing and detailing were carried out with 0.019 × 0.025-in TMA archwires, incorporating minor bends to refine incisor angulation and to establish optimal intercuspation. Settling elastics were used to improve posterior occlusion.

After debonding, CBCT scan was performed to confirm bone availability and root parallelism in the mandibular ante-

rior region. This ensured an adequate foundation for implant placement without encroaching on adjacent root structures.

Three endosseous implants were placed in positions corresponding to 31 and 42. A healing period of 4 months was allowed for osseointegration, after which screw retained implant supported crowns were fabricated and delivered. Final occlusion showed ideal space restoration, maintenance of Class I molar and canine relation, and proper alignment of arches.

Retention was achieved using a fixed bonded retainer in the mandibular anterior region (canine to canine) to preserve alignment and a maxillary removable retainer to maintain transverse stability.

Results

Result Post Treatment Introral and Extraoral

1. Class I molar and canine relation maintained.
2. Ideal space distribution in the mandibular anterior segment.
3. Implant supported crowns provided excellent aesthetics, phonetics, and functional occlusion.
4. Patient reported significant improvement in smile aesthetics and confidence.

Discussion

The management of patients with missing mandibular incisors presents unique challenges in orthodontics and restorative dentistry. The absence of these teeth affects anterior guidance, phonetics, aesthetics, and smile harmony. Orthodontic treatment must be carefully coordinated with prosthodontic planning to achieve both functional and aesthetic rehabilitation.

1. **Biomechanical Considerations:** Maintaining the Class I molar and canine relationship was crucial, as altering the antero-posterior occlusion would have compromised function. The use of a sequential archwire system allowed for gentle alignment, space distribution, and torque control, minimizing risks of root resorption and periodontal compromise. Rectangular stainless steel archwires provided stability during space maintenance, ensuring that adequate and symmetrical space was preserved for implant placement.
2. **Interdisciplinary Planning:** The decision to restore the missing teeth with implants was based on the patient's age, periodontal health, and sufficient alveolar bone volume. Implant supported crowns provide a fixed, aesthetics, and functionally stable solution compared with removable or resin bonded prostheses, which are often less durable and aesthetically inferior in the long term. The timing of implant placement was critical post-growth completion to ensure long-term stability and to prevent infraocclusion.
3. **Literature Support:** Kokich (2004) emphasized that orthodontic space management prior to implant placement is essential for ideal restorative outcomes, as improper space distribution may lead to compromised aesthetics or difficulty in implant placement. Proffit et al. (2018) described the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in such cases, underscoring that implants should only be placed once growth has ceased to avoid occlusal discrepancies. Several clinical reports have demonstrated predictable aesthetic and functional outcomes when orthodontics is combined with implant-based rehabilitation in cases of anterior tooth agenesis or traumatic loss.
4. **Clinical Significance:** This case underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration. Orthodontics alone could not have restored the patient's aesthetics and function, but it created the foundation for implant placement by aligning adjacent teeth and ensuring adequate root angulation and space. The final result demonstrates that combining orthodontic biomechanics with implant prosthodontics can achieve long-term occlusal stability, aesthetics, and patient satisfaction.

Conclusion

This case demonstrates that successful management of patients with missing mandibular incisors requires a coordinated orthodontic prosthodontic approach. Orthodontic treatment played a critical role in redistributing and maintaining space, controlling root angulation, and preserving the existing Class I molar and canine relationships. Sequential archwire mechanics allowed for gentle alignment and space preparation, ensuring a biologically sound foundation for

implant placement. The subsequent placement of three mandibular implants provided a definitive, aesthetic and functional replacement for the missing teeth, restoring anterior guidance, phonetics, and smile aesthetics.

The outcome highlights several clinical principles:

1. Space creation and root positioning must be orthodontically optimized before implant placement.
2. Interdisciplinary treatment planning between orthodontist and prosthodontist is indispensable to achieve harmonious aesthetic and functional results.
3. Implant Supported prostheses represent a stable, long-term solution for anterior tooth loss in young adults once skeletal growth has ceased.

Overall, the integration of orthodontic biomechanics with implant prosthodontics can achieve predictable and stable results, significantly improving oral function, smile aesthetics and patient satisfaction.

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